

Measuring climate resilience and adaptive capacity across European regions

Abstract: This registered report has been prepared for the Resilienship proposal HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-01 - Better prepared regional and local authorities to adapt to climate change. It reviews most recent literature (since 2015) on indicator-based resilience and adaptive capacity assessments, extracts and describes the indicators used and outline methodology to evaluate vulnerability and resilience across European (EU) regions. The analysis underpins and feeds into the planned activities of the Resilienship proposal.

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1. Introduction and scope

There is mounting evidence about how frequency and severity of climate and weather extremes are amplified by global warming, and how every additional increment of warming levels magnifies the changes in such extremes in the future. These extremes range from frequent and extended occurrences of heatwaves and forest fires to droughts, floods and hurricanes⁽¹⁾. According to the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change⁽²⁾, the EU and the global community are not fully prepared to cope with the increasing intensity, frequency and pervasiveness of climate change impacts, especially as temperatures continue to rise up.

As a foundation for policy coherence on adaptation, the European Climate Law proposal is designed to integrate the Paris Agreement's global goal on adaptation and Sustainable Development Goal 13 action into European law. The proposal calls on the EU and its Member States to accelerate the progress to enhance adaptive capacity and strengthen resilience to tackle climate change impacts. Monitoring, reporting and evaluation schemes are essential to measure such progress. Hence, the Commission calls for developing suitable indicators and a resilience assessment framework at local, regional, national or transnational scale in line with work in the UNFCCC Adaptation Committee⁽²⁾.

Resilience and adaptive capacity are strongly tangled containing similar consideration for assessment design⁽³⁾⁻⁽⁵⁾. Resilience in the context of disaster risk reduction has been described as “the ability of a system, community or society exposed to hazards to resist, absorb, accommodate to and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner”⁽⁶⁾. In the field of climate change, the IPCC defines resilience as “the capacity of social, economic and environmental systems to cope with a hazardous event or trend or disturbance, responding or reorganizing in ways that maintain their essential function, identity and structure, while also maintaining the capacity for adaptation learning and transformation”⁽⁷⁾. On the other hand, adaptive capacity is “the ability of systems, institutions, humans and other organisms to adjust to potential damage, to take advantage of opportunities, or to respond to consequences”⁽⁸⁾, and refers to capabilities, resources and institutions for implementing effective adaptation measures⁽⁹⁾.

Despite the copious body of literature on how resilience and adaptive capacity could be framed and conceptualized⁽¹⁰⁾⁻⁽¹⁴⁾, no single framework has been found to be broad and flexible enough to serve the various interpretations and policy designs. Practical applications of adaptive capacity and resilience embrace economic wealth, technology, information and skills, infrastructure, institutions, equity, resource-dependency, demographics and interconnectivity as main determinants⁽¹⁴⁾⁻⁽¹⁷⁾. The scope of this study is to develop a composite indicator to measure climate resilience and adaptive capacity for European regions using the most recent data and innovative methodological choices. The collected data and the index rankings will be used to develop a web-based data provision platform to visualize the adaptive capacity and resilience values along with a decision support tool which provides the opportunity for decision makers to test alternative indicators and methodological choices to build the index.

2. Data and methods

2.1 Data collection and indicators

In the first stage of our study, we reviewed the most recent literature (since 2015 up to present) on indicator-based resilience and adaptive capacity assessments. Table 1 includes the list of the articles with information on the location of interest, and type of hazard targeted in each study.

Table 1. List of resilience and adaptive capacity articles reviewed in this study.

ID	DOI	Type	# citations	Country	Scale	Scope	Hazard
ABG2020	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sci-totenv.2020.140905	Resilience	0	Spain	Urban	Socioeconomic Vulnerability	Flash flooding
TPG2020	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-020-02479-5	Resilience/Adaptive capacity	0	China	Household	Resilience	Landslide
GMM2020	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.110268	Adaptive capacity	0	Romania	Urban	Vulnerability	Heat waves
KAK2020	https://doi.org/10.3390/cli7040056	Adaptive capacity	1	Bangladesh	Regional	Vulnerability	Storm surge
VKG2020	https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab6499	Adaptive capacity	3	India	Regional	Social Vulnerability	Hydro-climatic hazards
HPP2020	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-020-04155-w	Resilience	0	China	Provincial	Resilience	Hazard independent
WQL2020	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106088	Resilience	0	China	Regional/Provincial	Resilience	Climate-related hazard
BMS2020	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106197	Adaptive capacity	5	India	Regional	Vulnerability	Drought
GNN2020	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105787	Adaptive capacity	14	India	Regional/municipalities	Vulnerability	Climate-related hazard
KSP2019	https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-018-1061-8	Adaptive capacity	8	India	Municipality	Vulnerability	Coastal flood
SSC2019	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.09.052	Adaptive capacity	12	Brazil	Regional	Vulnerability	Coastal flood
MMH2019	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0221585	Resilience/Adaptive capacity	4	Italy	Municipality	Resilience	Hazard independent
NB2019	https://doi.org/10.3390/su11236695	Resilience	2	Pakistan	Provincial	Vulnerability	Flood
ROB2019	https://doi.org/10.3390/su11164341	Resilience	3	Colombia	Municipality	Vulnerability	Flood
LFL2019	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118406	Resilience	6	China	Provincial	Resilience	Flood
AMA2019	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0219393	Resilience	4	Ethiopia	Provincial/Regional	Resilience	Climate change-induced shocks
KM2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2017.10.025	Resilience	30	United States	Urban	Resilience	Storm
MMS2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.06.060	Adaptive capacity	7	Italy	Regional/Provincial	Adaptive capacity	Hazard independent
AS2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.02.271	Adaptive capacity	21	Brazil	Census	Vulnerability	Flood/Flash flood
DMM2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2017.09.049	Adaptive capacity	12	Romania	LAU (local administrative unit)	Resilience	Drought
FZG2018	https://doi.org/10.1186/s40677-018-0106-4	Adaptive capacity	1	Ethiopia	Urban (municipality)	Vulnerability	Flood

AKS2018	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.kjss.2017.06.009	Adaptive capacity	35	Ghana	Municipality	Vulnerability	Temperature and rainfall
MCM2018	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0190808	Adaptive capacity	9	Brazil	Municipalities	Vulnerability	Climate-related hazard
JC2018	https://european-crt.org/files/typology-final-report.pdf	Adaptive capacity	0	Europe	NUTS3	Adaptive capacity	Climate-related hazard
WMB2017	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2016.10.003	Adaptive capacity	11	Europe	National (NUTS0)	Adaptive capacity	Drought
HRS2017	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accre.2017.11.002	Adaptive capacity	21	Indonesia	Urban	Vulnerability	Coastal flood
PKA2017	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.03.047	Adaptive capacity	51	India	Household	Vulnerability	Drought
MRR2017	http://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-016-2718-x	Adaptive capacity	5	India	District	Vulnerability	Coastal flood
FBR2017	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.07.054	Adaptive capacity	6	New Zealand	Census	Vulnerability	Hazard independent
YOO2017	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-017-2985-1	Adaptive capacity	15	Ghana	Community	Vulnerability	Flood
AMS2016	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.08.060	Adaptive capacity	15	Chile	Municipality	Adaptive capacity	Flood/Earthquake
PRD2016	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-015-1078-7	Adaptive capacity	11	Vietnam	Provincial	Vulnerability	Flood
ZSD2016	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.07.051	Adaptive capacity	19	China	Regional	Vulnerability	Air pollution
YKB2016	https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2015.1016142	Resilience	57	Korea	Municipality	Resilience	Hazard independent
IPB2016	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0162464	Adaptive capacity	46	Chile	Provincial	Vulnerability	Heat waves
WMB2016	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-016-1642-0	Adaptive capacity	64	Grenada	Island	Vulnerability	Flood
KR2016	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2015.06.018	Resilience	85	South Africa	Municipalities	Resilience	Flood
FBR2015	https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-015-1536-z	Adaptive capacity	6	Ecuador	Canton level	Vulnerability	Hazard independent
DGS2015	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-014-0369-1	Resilience	39	India	Islands	Resilience	Climate related disasters
LP2015	https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12141	Adaptive capacity	8	Taiwan	Municipalities	Vulnerability	Environmental hazards

In the second stage of the study, we collected the common indicators used in such assessments. The indicator dashboard includes overall 100 socioeconomic and geophysical indicators and instances reported from reviewed literature. We prioritized the use of socioeconomic data from Eurostat due to its role in coordinating statistical activities at Union level and more particularly inside the Commission. The geophysical indicators are computed based on various resources such as OpenStreetMap, Natura 2000 and NASA database. Our priority is to use the most recent data with lowest number of missing values. For instance, the share of protected lands from the total area was estimated on the basis of the extension of the Special Protection Areas (SPA) and the Sites of Community Importance (SCIs) under the Natura 2000 Network ^{(18),(19)}. For the ecological corridors, we used the database developed by the European Environment Agency in the framework of the EU Copernicus programme ⁽²⁰⁾. The composite European Quality of Government Index (EQI) was used as a sole indicator of the institutional capacity ⁽²¹⁾. Table 2 and 3 illustrate the initial set of indicators and instances classified at NUTS2 level.

Table 2. List of socioeconomic indicators (identifier 1) and instances (identifier 2) at NUTS 2 level that will be used in this study.

ID	CODE	Indicator	Instance	Code EUSTAT	Year
1	GDP	Gross domestic product	At current market prices	nama_10r_3gdp	2018
2	GDPpps	Gross domestic product	Purchasing power standards (PPS)	nama_10r_3gdp	2018
2	GDPpc	Gross domestic product	Per capita	nama_10r_3gdp	2018
2	GDPpps-pc	Gross domestic product	Purchasing power standards (PPS) per capita	nama_10r_3gdp	2018
2	GDPdens	Gross domestic product	Density	nama_10r_3gdp	2018
1	GVA	Gross Value added	At basic prices	nama_10r_3gva	2018
2	GVApc	Gross Value added	Per capita	nama_10r_3gva	2018
2	GVAagr	Gross Value added	Share of agriculture, forestry and fishing sector	nama_10r_3gva	2018
2	GVAind	Gross Value added	Share of industry (except construction) sector	nama_10r_3gva	2018
2	GVAmnf	Gross Value added	Share of manufacturing sector	nama_10r_3gva	2018
2	GVAcnstr	Gross Value added	Share of construction sector	nama_10r_3gva	2018
2	GVAgr	Gross Value added	Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices by NUTS 2 regions	nama_10r_2gvagr	2019
1	HHI	Income of households	Income by Million euro	nama_10r_2hhinc	2018
2	HHIpc	Income of households	Per capita	nama_10r_2hhinc	2018
2	HHIpps	Income of households	Purchasing power standards (PPS)	nama_10r_2hhinc	2018
2	HHIpps-pc	Income of households	Purchasing power standards (PPS) per capita	nama_10r_2hhinc	2018
1	EMPL	Employment	Total	nama_10r_3empers	2018
2	EMPLEap	Employment	By age (15-64) - economically active population	lfst_r_lfe2emp	2019
2	EMPLf	Employment	By age (15-64) and by sex (Female)	lfst_r_lfe2emp	2019
2	EMPLagr	Employment	Share of agriculture, forestry and fishing sector	lfst_r_lfe2en2	2019
2	EMPLind	Employment	Share of industry (except construction) sector	lfst_r_lfe2en2	2019
2	EMPLcnstr	Employment	Share of construction sector	lfst_r_lfe2en2	2019
2	EMPLr	Employment	Employment rate (by age 15-64)	lfst_r_lfe2emprrt	2019
2	EMPLrf	Employment	Employment rate (by age-15-64 and by sex- Female)	lfst_r_lfe2emprrt	2019
2	EMPLkt	Employment	Share of Technology and knowledge-intensive sectors	htec_emp_reg2	2019
2	EMPLktf	Employment	Share of Technology and knowledge-intensive sectors - Female	htec_emp_reg2	2019
1	UEMPL	Unemployment	By age (15-74)	lfst_r_lfu3pers	2019
2	UEMPLf	Unemployment	By age (15-74) and by sex (Female)	lfst_r_lfu3pers	2019
2	UEMPLr	Unemployment	Unemployment rate (by age-15-74)	lfst_r_lfu3rt	2019
2	UEMPLrf	Unemployment	Unemployment rate (by age-15-64 and by sex- Female)	lfst_r_lfu3rt	2019
2	LUEMPLr	Unemployment	Long term unemployment rate (by age-15-74)	lfst_r_lfu2ltu	2019
2	LUEMPLrf	Unemployment	Long term unemployment rate (by age-15-74 and sex-Female)	lfst_r_lfu2ltu	2019

1	AROPE	People at risk of poverty or social exclusion	Percentage	ilc_peps11	2018
1	MatDep	Severe material deprivation rate	Percentage	ilc_mddd21	2018
1	COMTr	Commuting rate for work	Percentage	lfst_r_lfe2ecomm	2019
2	COMTrf	Commuting rate for work	Percentage - Female	lfst_r_lfe2ecomm	2019
1	DPNDR	Age dependency ratio	Percentage of working-age population	demo_r_pjangrp3	2019
2	OADr	Old-age dependency ratio	Percentage of working-age population	demo_r_pjangrp3	2019
2	YADr	Young-age dependency ratio	Percentage of working-age population	demo_r_pjangrp3	2019
1	POPdens	Population density	People per sq. km of land area	demo_r_d3dens	2018
1	IMR	Infant Mortality Rate	Percentage	demo_r_minfind	2018
1	LE	Life Expectancy	At birth (less than 1 year age class)	demo_r_mlifexp	2018
2	LEf	Life Expectancy	At birth (less than 1 year age class)- Female	demo_r_mlifexp	2018
2	LEm	Life Expectancy	At birth (less than 1 year age class)- Male	demo_r_mlifexp	2018
1	LUS	Livestock	Total number of holdings	ef_olslsureg	2007
2	LUSh	Livestock	LSU of the holdings with livestock	ef_olslsureg	2007
1	LC	Land cover	Land cover per sq. Km	lan_lcv_ovw	2015
2	LCA	Land cover	Percentage of Artificial land	lan_lcv_ovw	2015
2	LCC	Land cover	Percentage of Cropland	lan_lcv_ovw	2015
2	LCw	Land cover	Percentage of Woodland	lan_lcv_ovw	2015
2	LCg	Land cover	Percentage of Grassland	lan_lcv_ovw	2015
2	LCwa	Land cover	Percentage of Water	lan_lcv_ovw	2015
2	LCwet	Land cover	Percentage of Wetland	lan_lcv_ovw	2015
1	LU	Land use	Land use per sq. Km	lan_use_ovw	2015
2	Luagr	Land use	Percentage of Agriculture	lan_use_ovw	2015
2	LUfa	Land use	Percentage of Fishing and aquaculture	lan_use_ovw	2015
2	Lumq	Land use	Percentage of Mining and quarrying	lan_use_ovw	2015
2	Luen	Land use	Percentage of Energy production	lan_use_ovw	2015
2	LUwwt	Land use	Percentage of Water and waste treatment	lan_use_ovw	2015
2	LUCnstr	Land use	Percentage of Construction	lan_use_ovw	2015
2	Luinf	Land use	Percentage of Transport, telecommunication, energy distribution, storage, protective works	lan_use_ovw	2015
1	IRRa	Irrigation	Share of irrigable area	ef_poirrig	2013
2	IRRagr	Irrigation	Share of Utilized agricultural area	ef_poirrig	2013
2	IRRuua	Irrigation	Irrigable land over the total utilized agricultural area	ef_poirrig	2010
1	EDUPI	Education	Primary and lower secondary education (levels 1 and 2)	educ_uoe_enra15	2016
2	EDUPh	Education	Tertiary education (levels 5-8)	educ_uoe_enra15	2016
2	EDUPt	Education	By age group (15-24)	educ_uoe_enra14	2016
2	EDUI	Education	Share of population with primary and lower secondary education (levels 1 and 2)	edat_lfse_04	2019

2	EDUlf	Education	Share of Female population with primary and lower secondary education (levels 1 and 2)	edat_lfse_04	2019
2	EDUhh	Education	Share of population with tertiary education (levels 5-8)	edat_lfse_04	2019
2	EDUhf	Education	Share of female population with tertiary education (levels 5-8)	edat_lfse_04	2019
1	GERD	R&D expenditure	Percentage of gross domestic product (GDP)	rd_e_gerdreg	2017
1	RD	R&D personnel and researchers	Total number	rd_p_persreg	2017
2	RDr	R&D personnel and researchers	Percentage of active population	rd_p_persreg	2017
2	RDrf	R&D personnel and researchers	Percentage of Female	rd_p_persreg	2018
1	PAT	Patent	Total number	pat_ep_rtot	2012
2	PATpmi	Patent	Per million inhabitants	pat_ep_rtot	2012
1	HIA	Internet access	Percentage of households	isoc_r_iacc_h	2019
2	IIA	Internet access	Percentage of individuals	isoc_r_iuse_i	2019
1	HP	Health personnel	Total number	hlth_rs_prsrg	2016
2	HPpc	Health personnel	Inhabitants per health personnel	hlth_rs_prsrg	2016
1	HOSb	Hospital beds	Total number	hlth_rs_bdsrg	2016
2	HOSbi	Hospital beds	Inhabitants per hospital beds	hlth_rs_bdsrg	2016
1	MRN	Road, rail and navigable in land waterways networks	Share of Major roads(km)	tran_r_net	2018
1	VEH	Stock of vehicles	Total number	tran_r_vehst	2017
2	VEHr	Stock of vehicles	Share of Stock of vehicles	tran_r_vehst	2017
1	SE	Soil erosion	Agricultural areas and natural grassland	aei_pr_soiler	2016
1	EQI	Quality of Government	European Quality of Government Index	eqi_data_long17_v2	2017

Table 3. List of geophysical indicators at NUTS 2 level that will be used in this study.

Code	Indicator	Unit	Year	Source
NAP	Airports	Number	2017	WRI (https://openflights.org/data.html)
APpc	Airports per head of population	Number per 100000 people	2017	WRI (https://openflights.org/data.html)
NP	Ports	Number	2019	OCHA (https://data.humdata.org/dataset/world-port-index)
Ppc	Ports per head of population	Number per 100000 people	2019	OCHA (https://data.humdata.org/dataset/world-port-index)
NPP	Power plants	Number	2018	WRI (https://datasets.wri.org/dataset/globalpowerplantdatabase)
NPPpc	Power plants per head of population	Number per 100000 people	2018	WRI (https://datasets.wri.org/dataset/globalpowerplantdatabase)
RDN	Length of major road network	Km	2014	OpenStreetMaps (http://download.geofabrik.de)
RDNr	Extension of the roads as a share of the total area	Km per Km2	2014	OpenStreetMaps (http://download.geofabrik.de)
RLN	Length of railway network	Km	2014	OpenStreetMaps (http://download.geofabrik.de)
RLNr	Extension of the railway network as a share of the total area	Km per Km2	2014	OpenStreetMaps (http://download.geofabrik.de)
PA	Protected areas	KM2	2019	EEA (Natura 2000 & CDDA)

PAr	Share of protected areas	%	2019	EEA (Natura 2000 & CDDA)
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2.2 Data preprocessing and analysis

Data preprocessing shall address several statistical issues such as missing data, multi-collinearity, dimension reduction and internal consistency. We propose the following statistical approaches for each step of the data preprocessing:

Missing data: In the case of less than five percent missing values, we may exclude the observations suggested by OECD⁽²²⁾. Otherwise, the data can be imputed using unconditional mean/median/mode imputation where sample mean (median, mode) of the non-missing values for the given individual indicator replaces the missing values, or regression imputation where missing values are substituted by the predicted values obtained from regression. The limitation of the unconditional mean/median/mode imputation is that the imputed value may become a biased estimator of the population mean (median or mode), and the sample variance underestimates true variance and consequently underestimating the uncertainty in the composite due to the imputation. The regression imputation computes the missing values using a regression between individual indicator hosting the missing value and highly correlated variables as the regressors (e.g. estimating poverty missing values with GDP). A key limitation is the underestimation of the standard errors and uncertainty issues that can be alleviated using multiple imputation techniques. Multiple imputation estimates the missing data using a Monte Carlo random process to produce a distribution of the parameters of interest on each data set, together with the standard errors⁽²²⁾.

Multicollinearity: to avoid high intercorrelation between variables, multicollinearity tests are essential. When multicollinearity exceeds a certain threshold, standard errors and variances are inflated, possibly biasing the overall results^{(22),(23)}. In order to detect multicollinearity among the variables, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) can be used. Various VIF threshold values have been considered for the collinearity test^{(22),(24)–(26)}. Researchers working on risk, vulnerability and resilience have been considering VIF = 10 as the cut-off value^{(26),(27)}.

Dimension reduction: In this study we are dealing with 100 indicators, many of them are highly correlated. Several methods such as principal component analysis (PCA) and factor analysis could be implemented to reduce the dimension of the indicators' dashboard. PCA has been widely used in most of the vulnerability related literature^{(27)–(30)}. With the aid of PCA, the data could be transformed to principal components (factors) which are uncorrelated. Besides, the first principal component accounts for the maximum possible proportion of the variance of the data set⁽²²⁾. According to OECD handbook, “largest factor loadings are assigned to the indicators that have the largest variations which is a desirable property for cross-comparisons”. Hence, the indicators with higher factor loading should be chosen from the dashboard as the analysis inputs⁽²²⁾.

Internal consistency: the Cronbach coefficient alpha (c-alpha) is the most common estimate of internal consistency of the indicators in a model or survey^{(22),(31),(32)}. Cronbach's Alpha evaluates the degree to which a set of items (indicators) measures an analogous unidimensional object⁽³³⁾. In statistical terms, C-alpha is a measure of the portion of total variability within individual indicators based on correlations. C-alpha values above 0.7 have been considered an acceptable range to measure reliability^{(22),(31),(34),(35)}.

The analysis includes three main stages namely normalization, weighting and aggregation. For each stage, the following methodological choices can be employed:

Normalization: Indicators should be normalized to “render them comparable”⁽²²⁾. There are several procedures to normalize the data (min-max, z-scores, distance to a benchmark, balance of opinions, etc.) which should be selected regarding the typology of the data set and also the further aggregation issues.

Weighting and Aggregation: Most frequently in similar studies equal weights are assigned to all indicators which are then aggregated by a simple arithmetic mean^{(30),(36),(37)}. This compensatory aggregation means that a lower performance of one indicator can be compensated by a higher performance of another indicator. In some cases a non-compensatory or partial non-compensatory approaches may be more appropriate⁽²²⁾. In general, the most popular aggregation operators are Pythagorean means (arithmetic mean, geometric mean and harmonic mean), median, weighted mean, minimum and maximum which can be extracted from generalized mean function. In order to add some degree of complexity to the aforesaid operators, Ordered Weighted Average (OWA) could be used which generalizes the weighted average, minimum and maximum operators and generates “in between”

evaluation. In the case of non-compensatory approaches, the aggregation shall be done in fuzzy environment using fuzzy sets conjunction and disjunction presented by T-norms and T-conorms. These operators assign a weight to any possible subset of criteria rather than to a single criterion, as in the case of weighted average. This means that the weight or importance assigned to a subset of criteria can be equal, higher or lower than the importance attributed to the sum of the single elements of the subset ^{(38),(39)}. Figure 1 illustrates a range of aggregation operators.

Figure 1. Aggregation operators modified from ⁽³⁸⁾

Web-based data provision platform: The last stage of the analysis is devoted to developing an open-source GIS decision support web platform which provides technological support for complex forms of decision-making. The data produced in this study will be spatially presented with a public access to the source data. The distinction between the proposed tool and the available GIS risk platforms such as JRC Risk Data Hub and ThinkHazard would be the possibility to elaborate on the methodological choices used to normalize, weight and aggregate the adaptive capacity and resilience indicators. This provides better insights for policy makers on the strength and weaknesses of the area of interest that should be fed into CCA policies and practices.

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